

STUDYING THE PHOTOELECTRIC CHARACTERISTICS OF CuTlSe₂ SINGLE CRYSTAL

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Controlled radiation doses, characterisation techniques (such as electrical measurements, spectroscopy, and microscopy), and theoretical modeling are usually necessary to completely comprehend the precise effects of gamma radiation on the electrophysical characteristics of CuTlSe₂ single crystals. These studies direct the optimization of CuTlSe₂ for a range of technological applications and shed light on the basic mechanisms underlying the observed modifications [1-3].

CuTlS(Se) compounds, with their complex band structures and multiple chemical bonds, lead to the emergence of new physical and chemical properties. The formation of such properties enables the development of energy converters, photodetectors, and thermoelectric elements that can operate at low-temperature ranges. Therefore, thallium chalcogenides could serve as base materials for fabricating devices with novel characteristics.

This study examines the effects of ionizing radiation on the electrical and photoelectric properties of p-CuTlSe₂ single crystals and investigates their radiation resistance. The electrical properties of CuTlSe₂ single crystals were studied in the 100–300 K temperature range under both low and high electric fields. Silver paste was used for ohmic electrical contacts, with a contact spacing of $L = 6.5$ mm. Measurements were carried out using a B7-30 universal ammeter-voltmeter in the 0–20 V range ($E \sim 10\text{--}10^5$ V/cm).

The electrical conductivity of p-CuTlSe₂ single crystals was studied under different gamma radiation doses in the 100–300 K range. The dependence of $\ln(\sigma) \sim 1/T$ was analyzed before irradiation, and it was found that in p-CuTlSe₂ single crystals, conductivity is determined by energy levels with an activation energy of 0.01 eV in the 100–250 K temperature range and 0.22 eV in the 250–300 K range. As temperature increases, a weak increase in conductivity is observed in the low-temperature range, while an exponential increase is noted in the high-temperature range. It has been determined that conductivity in CuTlSe₂ single crystals occurs with the involvement of Se vacancies. The activation energy determined from the $\ln(\sigma) \sim 1/T$ dependence is related to the concentration of selenium vacancies. It has been demonstrated that at radiation doses below $D_\gamma < 500$ krad, the electrical conductivity of the crystal decreases. This indicates that defects generated during irradiation have a donor nature, partially compensating for the initial acceptor-type defects. At higher radiation doses ($D_\gamma > 500$ krad), electrical conductivity increases, indicating that the radiation-induced defects are of acceptor type. This suggests that gamma radiation generates both donor-type and acceptor-type defects in p-CuTlSe₂ single crystals, and their conductivity varies depending on the defect concentration. The nature of radiation-induced defects

is similar to that of structural defects, with only the defect concentration changing based on the radiation dose.

Figure 1. Temperature dependence of photoconductivity ($\sigma \sim 1/T$) in initial and gamma-irradiated CuTlSe₂ single crystals at radiation doses of 0, 100, 200, and 500 krad.

As seen from the graph, the photocurrent increases with rising temperature. This observed effect is due to the narrowing of the crystal's bandgap with increasing temperature. The $\ln(\sigma) \sim 1/T$ dependence consists of two parts, and the activation energy values determined from the linear segment of the curve were 0.1 eV and 0.25 eV, respectively. In the low-temperature range (110–250 K), the photocurrent increases weakly, while in the high-temperature range (250–300 K), the rate of increase becomes more significant (curve 1).

Thus, the electrical and photoelectric properties of CuTlSe₂ single crystals depend on the concentration of initial defects in the crystal lattice, with conductivity being influenced by the concentration of selenium vacancies. Under gamma radiation, the ratio of radiation-induced defects in the cation and anion sublattices varies depending on the radiation dose. As a result, in the initial stage of irradiation, conductivity decreases due to the compensation of initial defects. At higher doses, conductivity increases due to the dominance of anion defects. The dependence of photocurrent on radiation dose indicates that radiation-induced defects act as recombination centers, whose concentration depends on the radiation dose.

The results show that in CuTlSe₂ single crystals, the nature and concentration of radiation-induced defects vary with radiation dose, allowing for controlled modification of crystal properties.

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